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Anti Kant – Epistemological Red Lines And Beyond

Research article

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Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

This paper explores various investigations into the intersections of philosophical thought and scientific theory.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

We examine the points of contact between Einstein's Special Theory of Relativity (ESTR) and Kant's epistemology. Additionally, the relationship between ESTR and Einstein's General Theory of Relativity is developed.

RESULTS:

For centuries, Kantian philosophy, especially the dualism between *phenomena* (what we can experience) and *noumena* (what lies beyond our understanding), has established rigorous boundaries within the philosophy of knowledge. While Kant's critical division was innovative in Kant's time, it now serves as an epistemological barrier, a conceptual 'red line' that many have been hesitant to cross. This publication highlights an urgent and provocative critique of Kant's entrenched epistemological distinctions. Kant's imposed epistemological constraints are found to be unjustified.

CONCLUSION:

We are all called to definitively leave behind Kant's artificially constructed epistemological boundaries which unnecessarily limits our possibilities.

Keywords:

Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

Immanuel Kant stands as a pivotal figure in the history of Western philosophy, fundamentally shaking the epistemological relationship between knowledge and reality. Kant's critical philosophy, particularly articulated in the *Critique of Pure Reason*, lays the groundwork for Western epistemology by differentiating between two realms: noumena and phenomena. Noumena refer to things as they are in themselves, independent of human perception, while phenomena are the appearances of these things as they are experienced by observers. This distinction is crucial, as it underscores Kant's argument that our knowledge is inherently limited to the latter; we can only know the world as it appears to us, not as it is in its essence.

Kant's philosophy arose during a time of significant intellectual upheaval, amidst the debates of rationalism and empiricism.

Rationalism and empiricism represent two foundational approaches to epistemology, each offering distinct perspectives on the nature of knowledge. *Rationalism*, exemplified by philosophers such as René Descartes, Baruch Spinoza, and Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz, posits that reason is the primary source of knowledge. *Rationalists* argue that certain concepts and knowledge are innate, existing independently of sensory experience. Descartes, for instance, famously asserted "Cogito, ergo sum" ("I think, therefore I am"), emphasizing the role of doubt and introspection as pathways to undeniable truths. In this view, *mathematical truths* and *logical deductions* are seen as examples of knowledge accessible through reason alone.

Conversely, empiricism, championed by figures like John Locke, George Berkeley, and David Hume, contends that knowledge arises from sensory experience. Empiricists assert that the mind begins as a *tabula rasa*, or blank slate, and that all ideas originate from our interactions with the world. Locke, in his *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, argues that knowledge is built upon sensory experiences and reflections upon those experiences. Berkeley further posits that to be is to be perceived, challenging the notion of *a material world independent of observation*. Hume takes this further, questioning the very nature of causation and *induction*, emphasizing that our beliefs about the world stem from habit rather than rational certainty.

One of the principal differences between rationalism and empiricism lies in their foundational approaches to knowledge acquisition. Rationalists prioritize innate ideas and *deductive reasoning*, while empiricists emphasize observation and *inductive reasoning*. This fundamental divergence leads to contrasting views on the limits of human understanding; rationalists are more inclined to trust in the power of reason, whereas empiricists advocate for skepticism regarding claims that cannot be verified through experience.

In response to these competing perspectives, Kant sought to reconcile the two by proposing that while knowledge begins with experience, it is shaped by the mind's inherent structures. His synthesis of rationalist and empiricist ideas laid the groundwork for a different epistemology, influencing subsequent philosophical discourse on the nature of knowledge.

By synthesizing elements from both schools of thought, Kant advanced a unique epistemological framework. Kant posited that while empirical observations are essential for acquiring knowledge, they must be processed through a priori concepts that structure our experiences. Thus, the interplay between our sensory experiences and innate categories of understanding becomes central to his philosophy.

The implications of Kant's epistemology extend beyond mere academic discourse; they have influenced countless fields, from philosophy and cognitive science to the natural sciences. By asserting that our access to reality is mediated by our cognitive faculties, Kant challenged the notion of absolute objectivity, thereby inviting a critical examination of the limits of human reason.

In light of this, Kant's distinction between noumena and phenomena remains a foundational concept for subsequent philosophical inquiries. It compels us to consider the nature of reality and the potential barriers to our understanding, emphasizing the need for a rigorous examination of *the conditions under which knowledge is acquired*. As we engage with Kant's thought, we must confront the implications of his arguments for our understanding of science, perception, and the very essence of reality itself.

2. Material and methods

Definitions

Comoving Observer

DEFINITION 1 (Comoving Observer). A *comoving observer* O is an observer who shares the same velocity as the object being observed. As a result, the relative velocity between the observer and the object is zero, $v = 0$, even if both are in motion relative to other reference frames. This implies that the observer perceives “das Ding an sich”, the object as it really is, as “at rest,” with no time dilation or length contraction between them as both are in the same inertial frame of reference.

In point of fact, a co-moving observer O is able to measure the true (physical) characteristics and properties of a system, of a (quantum mechanical) entity et cetera which is unaffected by the observer’s movement. To push it to the epistemological extreme and to name the essence of the matter, a co-moving observer is measuring ‘das Ding an sich’, the entity as it is, “... das , was der Erscheinung der Materie, als Ding an sich selbst, zum Grunde liegt ... ” (see [Kant, 1790](#), p. 428), ‘that which underlies the appearance of matter, as a thing-in-itself’. However, under conditions of Einstein’s special theory of relativity, such a ‘Ding an sich’ is identical with the rest energy $E_{0,i}$. At this point and in complete accordance with Kant’s perspective, we confront a fundamental epistemological barrier that we must accept in order to find our inner epistemological peace: accept **either** Einstein’s special theory of relativity **or** Kant’s epistemological point of view, but not both. Each reader may answer this question for themselves; as for me, I have long since resolved it. Regardless, at this point, we must at least pose a fundamental question: To what extent, and for how long, are certain philosophical movements permitted to continue to ignore established, experimentally validated scientific knowledge? However that may be, Kant distinguishes between appearances (phenomena) and the thing-in-itself (noumenon). In this regard, special attention must be given to a particular characteristic of appearances, appearances are not things in themselves or ex negativo in Kant’s own words:

“Erscheinungen sind keine Dinge an sich selbst”

(see [Kant, 1790](#), p. 206)

Kant’s fundamental epistemological assertion and the central core of his far-reaching epistemological shockwaves producing publication *Kritik der reinen Vernunft* (*Critique of Pure Reason*), is that the thing-in-itself (*Ding an sich*) cannot be known.

“... wie Dinge an sich selbst ... seyn mögen, ist gänzlich außer unsrer Erkenntnißsphäre”

(see [Kant, 1790](#), p. 235)

Transcendental idealism or Kant’s epistemological stance asserts that things cannot be known in

their true nature and need to be considered as agnosticism. Agnosticism is the view that certain things, particularly metaphysical or transcendental matters, are either unknown or unknowable. In this sense, Kant's philosophy or transcendental idealism, particularly the dictum that our knowledge is based on phenomena rather than things-in-themselves (noumena) compels us to view the experimentally validated insights of Einstein's theory of special relativity as false and nonsensical an much more than this. Kant constrains our epistemological possibilities in accordance with the principle *cathedra mea, regulae meae*, insisting that we perceive objective reality unambiguously and without even a hint of proof, using only one epistemological eye. He argues that our second epistemological eye, which would allow us to investigate the thing-in-itself, is fundamentally blind. Thus, Kant prohibits an examination of objective reality with two epistemological eyes. In a sense, he renders us blind in one epistemological eye, compelling us to view objective reality like a one-eyed individual, possessing only a limited perspective on the world.

DEFINITION 2 (Relativistic Observer). A *relativistic observer* R is an observer whose relative velocity, v , with respect to the object observed is greater than zero or $v > 0$. If the relative velocity between this observer and the object reduces to zero, this observer becomes a comoving observer, perceiving the object as being at rest within the same inertial frame.

DEFINITION 3 (Trial). A trial, denoted by t , refers to a single execution or repetition of an experiment or random process, an observation et cetera at a certain (period of) time t , such as flipping a coin, rolling a die, or drawing a card from a deck. Each trial can have different possible outcomes, and an event is a specific outcome or set of outcomes we are interested in observing. The probability of an event might vary between trials.

DEFINITION 4 (Bernoulli trial). A **Bernoulli trial** is a fundamental concept in probability theory and statistics, representing an experiment or process that meets the following key conditions:

1. **Binary Outcome:** Each trial results in exactly one of two possible outcomes, typically labeled as "success" and "failure." These outcomes are mutually exclusive and exhaustive, meaning that no other result can occur.
2. **Constant Probability:** The probability of success, denoted as p , remains constant across all trials. Similarly, the probability of failure is $1 - p$, and this value does not change from trial to trial.
3. **Independence:** Each Bernoulli trial is independent of the others. The outcome of any one trial does not influence the outcomes of subsequent trials.

Mathematically, if X represents the outcome of a Bernoulli trial, then X is a random variable that can take the value 1 (for success) with probability p , and the value 0 (for failure) with probability $1 - p$. This can be written as:

$$P(X = 1) = p \quad \text{and} \quad P(X = 0) = 1 - p$$

Bernoulli trials are the building blocks for more complex probabilistic models, such as the binomial

distribution, where a fixed number of independent Bernoulli trials are conducted, and the total number of successes is counted.

The assumption of constant probability in a Bernoulli trial ensures consistency, allows for simpler mathematical treatment, and is aligned with the assumption of independent trials, making it a cornerstone of basic probability theory.

DEFINITION 5 (Random variable). Mathematically, a random variable $X_{R,t}$ represents the set of all possible outcomes of a random process, of an entity et cetera. Each individual outcome $x_{R,t} \in X_{R,t}$ corresponds to a real number, which signifies a potential realization of the random process at time t . The probability function $p(X_{R,t})$ maps these outcomes from the set of possible outcomes $X_{R,t}$ to the set of expectation values (which are real numbers $\mathbb{R}$), and is typically expressed something like:

$$p(X_{R,t}) : X_{R,t} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}.$$

and equally as:

$$p(X_{R,t}) : X_{R,t} \rightarrow E(X_{R,t}).$$

Types of Random Variables

Random variables are generally classified into two types:

- *Discrete random variables*: These take on a countable set of values. For instance, the number of heads in 10 flips of a coin is a discrete random variable.
- *Continuous random variables*: These can assume any value within a continuous range. An example might be the temperature measured at a given time, which can vary smoothly over an interval.

In classical probability theory, the sample space Ω is assumed to pre-exist as a complete set of all possible outcomes. A random variable $X_{R,t}$ simply maps these outcomes to corresponding real numbers, assigning measurable values to the elements of Ω .

However, the extension of this classical framework into one inspired by quantum mechanics challenges this static conception. In classical theory, the sample space Ω is treated as an abstract, unchanging entity, existing independently of any observations or natural phenomena. This conventional view holds that the possibilities contained within Ω are predetermined and merely await discovery through measurement or observation.

In contrast, a quantum-inspired approach suggests that $X_{R,t}$, representing a natural entity, does not adhere to this static model. Instead, the state of $X_{R,t}$ may exist in superposition, embodying multiple potential outcomes simultaneously.

Upon measurement and with the collapse of the superposition of $X_{R,t}$ or due to other circumstances, a single, observable outcome $x_{R,t}$ is realized. At this point, the exact value of the outcome $x_{R,t}$ becomes

known with certainty. However, such a specific outcome could manifested itself only according to the underlying probability $p(x_{R,t})$.

This notion aligns with the principles of quantum mechanics, where physical systems can exist in multiple states until observed.

Crucially, this perspective implies that the sample space Ω is not a fixed, pre-determined set of possibilities that exists independently of natural entities. Rather, the existence of a natural entity, such as $X_{R,t}$, which may itself vary and evolve over time, gives rise to the sample space. In this sense, the sample space is not external to the entity but is instead shaped by the entity's potential outcomes.

Furthermore, the probability function $p(x_{R,t})$ in this framework does not merely represent a lack of information or uncertainty about the system's state, as it might in classical theory. Rather, it reflects the underlying deterministic structure governing how certain outcomes manifest. The probability is an expression of the natural necessity by which one of the superimposed states of $X_{R,t}$ becomes reality upon observation, akin to the collapse of a quantum wavefunction.

In summary, this approach diverges significantly from the classical view by emphasizing the fluid, dynamic relationship between a natural entity and its corresponding sample space. Rather than viewing Ω as a pre-existing structure, it is the entity itself that generates the possible outcomes through its existence and evolution. This rethinking aligns more closely with the non-deterministic yet structured nature of quantum systems.

Classical logic

The concept of truth value, anticipated by Boole (see [Boole, 1854](#)) and Peirce (see [Peirce, 1885](#)), was explicitly introduced into logic and philosophy by Gottlob Frege in his 1892 influential paper (see [Frege, 1892](#)).

DEFINITION 6 (False). The symbol 0 denotes the numerical value zero. In classical logic and Boolean algebra, the concept of False (F) is represented by 0.

DEFINITION 7 (True). The symbol 1 denotes the numerical value one. In classical logic and Boolean algebra, the concept of True (T) is represented by 1.

Probability

Logic and probability theory are profoundly interconnected and evolving fields. Qualitative logic focuses on qualitative inferences, categorizing statements as either true or false, while numerical probabilities deal with quantifiable measures of likelihood. Despite this distinction, probability theory builds upon and expands classical logic, integrating its principles into a broader framework. The exact nature of probability may remain a subject for further investigation. With these clarifications

established, we can now define probabilities in this entry as follows. The following definitions also encompasses the possibility of negative probabilities.

DEFINITION 8 (Probability of occurrence). The probability of a single event, denoted as $p(X_{R,t})$, is determined by the degree of necessity with which that event must occur under the given circumstances, ranging from 0 (impossible) to 1 (certain).

DEFINITION 9 (Probability of non-occurrence). As soon as we know the probability with which a single event will occur, we simultaneously know the probability with which the same event will not occur. The probability of a single event, denoted as $1 - p(X_{R,t})$, is determined by the degree of necessity with which that event will not occur under the given circumstances, ranging from 0 (certain) to 1 (impossible).

Expectation value

The expectation value is a crucial tool for investigating the complexities of objective reality. This measure of relationship reflects the interplay between our observations, our expectations, and the underlying randomness of existence itself.

DEFINITION 10 (Expectation value). Mathematically, the expectation value $E(X_{R,t})$ of a single event $X_{R,t}$, is given by the formula:

$$E(X_{R,t}) = (X_{R,t}) \cdot p(X_{R,t}) \quad (1)$$

Here:

- $E(X_{R,t})$: denotes the expectation value.
- $X_{R,t}$: is the random variable.
- $p(X_{R,t})$: is the probability of $X_{R,t}$.

DEFINITION 11 (Expectation value). It is:

$$E(X_{R,t}^2) = (X_{R,t}) \cdot (X_{R,t}) \cdot p(X_{R,t}) = (X_{R,t}) \cdot E(X_{R,t}) \quad (2)$$

DEFINITION 12 (Expectation value). In general, it is

$$E(X_{R,t}^n) = \underbrace{(X_{R,t}) \cdots (X_{R,t})}_n \cdot p(X_{R,t}) \quad (3)$$

The essence of an expectation value lies in its role as a fundamental statistical concept that quantifies the central tendency or average outcome of a random variable. At its core, the expectation value is defined as the weighted sum of all possible outcomes, where the weights correspond to the likelihood of each outcome occurring.

$$E(X_R) = \sum_i E(X_{R,i}) = \sum_i X_{R,i} \cdot p(X_{R,i}) \quad (4)$$

DEFINITION 13 (Expectation value). Mathematically, the expectation value $E(\underline{X}_{R,t})$ of a single event $\underline{X}_{R,t}$, the other of $X_{R,t}$, is given by the formula:

$$E(\underline{X}_{R,t}) = (X_{R,t}) \cdot (1 - p(X_{R,t})) \quad (5)$$

DEFINITION 14 (Expectation value). Mathematically, the expectation value $E(\underline{X}_{R,t}^2)$ of a single event $\underline{X}_{R,t}$, the other of $X_{R,t}$, is given by the formula:

$$E(\underline{X}_{R,t}^2) = (X_{R,t}) \cdot (X_{R,t}) \cdot (1 - p(X_{R,t})) = (X_{R,t}) \cdot E(\underline{X}_{R,t}) \quad (6)$$

Variance

DEFINITION 15 (Variance). The variance (see [Kolmogoroff, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1933](#)) of a random variable $X_{R,t}$ is defined as:

$$\sigma(X_{R,t})^2 = E(X_{R,t}^2) - E(X_{R,t})^2 \quad (7)$$

$$= ((X_{R,t}) \cdot (X_{R,t}) \cdot p(X_{R,t})) - ((X_{R,t}) \cdot p(X_{R,t}))^2 \quad (8)$$

$$= ((X_{R,t}) \cdot (X_{R,t})) \cdot (p(X_{R,t}) - p(X_{R,t})^2) \quad (9)$$

$$= (X_{R,t}) \cdot (X_{R,t}) \cdot (p(X_{R,t}) \cdot (1 - p(X_{R,t}))) \quad (10)$$

$$= (X_{R,t}) \cdot (p(X_{R,t})) \cdot (X_{R,t}) \cdot (1 - p(X_{R,t})) \quad (11)$$

$$= E(X_{R,t}) \cdot E(\underline{X}_{R,t}) \quad (12)$$

where $E(X_{R,t})$ denotes the expectation of $X_{R,t}$.

In general, it is

$$(\underline{X}_{R,t}^2) = \frac{\sigma(X_{R,t})^2}{(p(X_{R,t})) \cdot (1 - p(X_{R,t}))} \quad (13)$$

Einstein's special theory of relativity

DEFINITION 16 (Energy-mass equivalence). Energy-mass equivalence is a fundamental principle of physics encapsulated by Einstein's (see [Einstein, 1905](#)) famous equation:

$$E_{R,t} = m_{R,t} \cdot c^2 \quad (14)$$

This formula states that the total or relativistic energy ($E_{R,t}$) of an object is equal to its relativistic (see also [Lewis and Tolman, 1909](#); [Tolman, 1912](#)) mass ($m_{R,t}$) multiplied by the square of the speed of light (c), highlighting the interchangeability of mass and energy.

DEFINITION 17 (Rest energy and relativistic energy). Rest energy refers to the intrinsic energy possessed by an object due to its rest mass, independent of its motion or external forces. It is given by the formula:

$$E_{0,t} = m_{0,t} \cdot c^2 = \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot E_{R,t} \quad (15)$$

where $E_{0,t}$ is the rest energy, $m_{0,t}$ is the rest mass, and c is the speed of light in a vacuum. The rest-energy is the energy of an object et cetera as measured by a co-moving observer 0, which is at relative rest with respect to the object itself. The rest-energy can be compared to Kant's notion of the *noumenon* or *thing-in-itself* (*das Ding an sich*), which refers to the intrinsic reality of an object as it is, independent of any human perception, measurement or relative movement. This relationship shows that even an object at rest has a significant amount of energy due to its mass. Rest energy is a special case of the more general

DEFINITION 18 (Rest energy and delta energy). The difference energy $\Delta E_{R,t}$ represents the discrepancy between the total relativistic energy ($E_{R,t}$) of an object and its rest energy ($E_{0,t}$) and is given as:

$$E_{\Delta,t} = E_{R,t} - E_{0,t} = E_{R,t} - \left(\left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot E_{R,t} \right) = \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot E_{R,t} \quad (16)$$

The difference energy $\Delta E_{R,t}$ can be viewed as a measure of the additional energy the object possesses due to influences such as external fields or thermodynamic conditions et cetera, which are not attributable only to its kinetic energy. In contrast to kinetic energy, which refers to the object's motion relative to an inertial frame, this difference energy encompasses other forms of energy too that the object has in relation to its rest energy. In general it is:

$$E_{R,t} = E_{0,t} + E_{\Delta,t} \quad (17)$$

DEFINITION 19 (Relativistic potential energy and relativistic kinetic energy). The relationship between relativistic potential energy and relativistic kinetic energy is foundational to understanding the dynamics of objects under relativistic conditions. The relationship between the relativistic potential energy and the relativistic kinetic energy is determined by the equation:

$$(E_{RP,t}) + (E_{RK,t}) = (E_{R,t}) \quad (18)$$

Here:

- $E_{RP,t} = \left(\left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot E_{0,t} \right) = \left(\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right) \cdot E_{R,t} \right)$: Represents the relativistic potential energy of an object.
- $E_{RK,t} = \left(m_{R,t} \cdot v^2 \right) = \left(\left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right) \cdot E_{R,t} \right)$: Represents the relativistic kinetic energy of an object as measured by the relativistic observer R .

- $E_{R,t} = (m_{R,t} \cdot c^2)$: Represents the total or relativistic energy of an object as measured by the relativistic observer R .

DEFINITION 20 (Ordinary energy and electromagnetic wave energy). The distinction between ordinary matter/energy $E_{OM,t}$ and electromagnetic wave energy $E_{W,t}$ helps to clarify the composition of the total relativistic energy $E_{R,t}$. Here, $E_{OM,t}$ refers to the conventional forms of energy possessed by matter, excluding contributions from electromagnetic radiation. On the other hand, $E_{W,t}$ represents the energy carried by electromagnetic waves/radiation, such as light or other forms of electromagnetic radiation. The equation

$$E_{OM,t} = E_{R,t} - E_{W,t} = \left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right) \cdot E_{R,t} \quad (19)$$

shows that the ordinary energy $E_{OM,t}$ is the difference between the total relativistic energy $E_{R,t}$ and the energy associated with electromagnetic waves $E_{W,t}$. This suggests that the total energy of a system can be divided into energy due to matter and energy due to electromagnetic fields. This distinction is particularly relevant in contexts of Einstein's general theory of relativity.

where:

- $E_{R,t}$: Energy, measured in joules (J), represents the total energy contained within a system or object from the point of view of an external (relativistic) observer.
- $E_{W,t} = \left(\frac{v}{c}\right) \cdot E_{R,t}$: Electromagnetic wave energy, represents the energy contained within the electromagnetic wave of a system or an object from the point of view of an external (relativistic) observer.
- $E_{OM,t} = \left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right) \cdot E_{R,t}$: Ordinary energy, represents the energy difference between $E_{R,t}$ and $E_{W,t}$ contained within a system or an object from the point of view of an external (relativistic) observer.

DEFINITION 21 (Time-Gravitational Field Equivalence). Time-gravitational field equivalence (see Barukčić, 2011, 2022) is a fundamental principle of physics, analogous to energy-mass equivalence, and can be conceptually described by the following equation:

$$t_{R,t} = g_{R,t} \cdot c^2 \quad (20)$$

This formula suggests that the total or relativistic time ($t_{R,t}$) experienced by an object is proportional to its relativistic gravitational field strength ($g_{R,t}$), multiplied by the square of the speed of light (c). This relationship highlights the conceptual interplay between time and the gravitational field, indicating their interconnected nature.

DEFINITION 22 (Rest Time and Relativistic Time). Rest time, or proper time, refers to the intrinsic time interval experienced by an object at rest in its own reference frame, independent of its motion or external forces. It is represented by the equation:

$$t_{0,t} = g_{0,t} \cdot c^2 = \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot t_{R,t} \quad (21)$$

where $t_{0,t}$ is the rest time (proper time), $g_{0,t}$ is the rest gravitational field strength, and c is the speed of light in a vacuum. The rest time is the duration measured by an observer co-moving with the object, in its own reference frame.

Analogous to Kant's notion of the *noumenon* or *thing-in-itself* (*das Ding an sich*), this rest time represents the intrinsic temporal nature of an object, independent of any external perception, measurement, or relative motion. It reveals that even in the absence of motion relative to an observer, the object possesses an inherent measure of time determined by its gravitational field.

Einstein's general theory of relativity

Einstein's General Relativity describes gravity not as a force, but as the curvature of spacetime caused by mass and energy. The Einstein's field equations (EFE) bridge the concepts of geometry and physics, suggesting that gravity is not merely a force but a manifestation of the curvature of spacetime itself. This perspective transforms our understanding of gravity from a Newtonian force to a geometric property, intertwining space, time, and matter in a single, cohesive framework. Physically, the EFE indicate how the presence of matter and energy curves the spacetime, resulting in gravitational effects. For instance, the presence of a massive object like the Earth causes spacetime around it to curve, which in turn governs the motion of objects, such as satellites, in its vicinity.

Einstein's Field Equations

DEFINITION 23 (Einstein's Field Equations). Einstein's field equations (EFE) are a set of ten interrelated differential equations in the theory of General Relativity that describe the fundamental interaction of gravitation as a result of spacetime being curved by matter and energy. They are given by:

$$\underbrace{R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}}_{\text{Left-handside}} = \underbrace{\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}}_{\text{Right-handside}} \quad (22)$$

where:

- $R_{\mu\nu}$: The Ricci curvature tensor, representing the degree to which the geometry of space is curved due to the matter distribution.

-
- R : The Ricci scalar, which is the trace of the Ricci tensor and gives an overall measure of the curvature.
 - $g_{\mu\nu}$: The metric tensor, which describes the geometry of spacetime.
 - Λ : The cosmological constant, representing the energy density of the vacuum.
 - G : The gravitational constant.
 - c : The speed of the light in vacuum.
 - π : The constant π (pi), also known as Archimedes' constant, is a fundamental mathematical constant representing the ratio of a circle's circumference to its diameter. This value is approximately 3.14159 and is an irrational number, meaning it cannot be expressed as a simple fraction and its decimal representation is infinite and non-repeating..
 - $T_{\mu\nu}$: The stress-energy tensor, which describes the density and flux of energy and momentum in spacetime.

The essence of the Einstein field equations can be summarized by the statement: Curvature tells matter how to move, and matter tells curvature how to bend. This reflects the dynamic relationship between spacetime geometry and the distribution of mass-energy. In this framework:

- The left-hand side of the equation, consisting of the Ricci curvature tensor, Ricci scalar, and metric tensor, encapsulates the geometric properties of spacetime.
- The right-hand side, represented by the stress-energy tensor, encompasses the physical content of spacetime, such as matter, radiation, and energy.

2.1. Axioms

2.1.1. Principium identitatis (Axiom I)

Lex identitatis seems to touch upon fundamental concepts in philosophy, particularly in the realm of logic, and science as such. In logical terms, this principle is formally expressed as “ $X = X$,” commonly known as the law of identity. In last consequence, this law asserts that something is identical to itself. However, if X is identical to X (law of identity), then it cannot be non-identical to X in the same respect, which aligns with the principle of contradiction. As known, the principle of contradiction posits that contradictory statements cannot both be true in the same sense simultaneously. The law of identity ensures the logical coherence and stability of scientific concepts, as it prevents logical contradictions and inconsistencies. This scientific perspective, rooted in objective reality, emphasises the significance of these principles in shaping our theorems, theories the understanding of reality and guiding coherent thought. It The interplay between identity and contradiction underscores essential natural laws of objective reality, providing us with a robust foundation for scientific inquiry.

Principium identitatis or **lex identitatis** or axiom I, is closely related to central problems of metaphysics, epistemology and of science as such. It turns out that it is more than rightful to assume that

$$+1 \equiv +1 \quad (23)$$

is true, otherwise there is every good reason to suppose that nothing can be discovered at all. With respect to a random variable, we obtain in its positive expression

$$+X \equiv +X \quad (24)$$

or in its negative expression

$$-X \equiv -X \quad (25)$$

Identity is not a static state but rather inherently involves a process of being distinct. The very nature of identity involves a dynamic quality of differentiation, identity, the nature of identity is to be different. Identity as the epitome of a self-identical or of self-reference is at the same time different from difference, identity is free from difference, identity is not difference, identity is at the same time the other of itself, identity is non-identity. Identity as simple equality with itself is determined by a non-being, by a non-being of its own other, by a non-being of difference, identity is different from difference. Identity is in its very own nature different and is in its own self the opposite of itself (symmetry). It is equally

$$-1 \equiv -1 \quad (26)$$

In general, $+1$ and -1 are distinguished, however these distinct are related to one and the same 1. Identity as a vanishing of otherness, therefore, is this distinguishedness in one relation. It is

$$0 \equiv +1 - 1 \equiv 0 \times 1 \equiv 0 \quad (27)$$

2.1.2. Principium contradictionis (Axiom II)

Principium contradictionis or **lex contradictionis** ^{1, 2, 3} or axiom II, the other of lex identitatis, the negative of lex identitatis, the opposite of lex identitatis, a complementary of lex identitatis, can be expressed mathematically as

$$+0 \equiv 0 \times 1 \equiv +1 \quad (28)$$

In addition to the above, from the point of view of mathematics, axiom II (equation 28) is equally the most simple mathematical expression and formulation of a (logical) contradiction.

2.1.3. Principium negationis (Axiom III)

Lex negationis or axiom III, is often mismatched with simple opposition. However, from the point of view of philosophy and other sciences, identity, contradiction, negation and similar notions are equally mathematical descriptions of the most simple laws of objective reality. What sort of natural process is negation at the end? Mathematically, we define principium negationis or lex negationis or axiom III as

$$\text{Negation}(0) \times 0 \equiv \neg(0) \times 0 \equiv +1 \quad (29)$$

where $\neg$ denotes (logical or natural) negation. In this context, there is some evidence that

$$\text{Negation}(1) \times 1 \equiv \neg(1) \times 1 = 0 \quad (30)$$

Logically, it follows that

$$\text{Negation}(1) \equiv 0 \quad (31)$$

¹Horn, Laurence R., "Contradiction", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Winter 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2018/entries/contradiction/>.

²Barukčić I. Aristotle's law of contradiction and Einstein's special theory of relativity. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics (JDDT)*. 15Mar.2019;9(2):125-43. <https://jddtonline.info/index.php/jddt/article/view/2389>

³Barukčić, Ilija. (2020, December 28). The contradiction is existing objectively and real (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4396106>

3. Results

In essence, Kant's noumenal world is forever beyond any human reach (see [Meillassoux, 2009](#)). Clearly, Kant's epistemology and his limits on human knowledge are too restrictive has not been immune to critique and development. From Hegel's quest for absolute knowledge to Nietzsche's dismantling of metaphysical boundaries, to the phenomenologists' challenge to Kant's categories, and finally to postmodern deconstructions of fixed truths—philosophers have continuously sought to go beyond Kant's epistemological red lines. In doing so, they question whether the limits Kant imposed are inherent to nature and human cognition. Thus, while Kant's philosophy remains important, its critics have opened up new avenues for understanding knowledge, truth, and objective reality, pushing beyond the red lines that Kant so carefully drew. By doing so, we can open the door to alternative ways of knowing that do not rest on the epistemological no-go as established by Kant. Unbounded by Kant's epistemological constraints implies a call to move beyond these boundaries and is also an invitation to re-imagine the possibilities of knowledge itself. What lies beyond the constraints of Kant's framework may be a richer, more fluid understanding of objective reality that allows for more expansive and nuanced ways of thinking.

In the course of these investigations, we aim to approach the problems posed by Kant from the perspectives of geometry and Einstein's theory of relativity. In relativity theory, there are concepts such as rest energy or the thing-in-itself, which cannot always be measured with absolute precision. However, these quantities can be calculated with high accuracy. This fact raises certain doubts about the absoluteness of the dogmas established by Kant. The concept of rest energy in relativity implies that energy and mass are equivalent and intrinsic properties of matter, resonating with Kant's idea of the thing-in-itself, yet measurable only indirectly through their effects. This challenges Kant's distinction between noumena (the thing-in-itself) and phenomena (the thing as it appears to us), as relativity blurs the lines between objective reality and measurement. Thus, the exactness of modern physical theories, combined with the inherent uncertainties in measurement, suggest a more complex interaction between knowledge and reality than Kant might have envisioned. This prompts a re-evaluation of the Kantian framework in light of contemporary scientific understanding, questioning whether his metaphysical principles can fully accommodate the insights provided by modern physics.

Pythagorean theorem

The Pythagorean Theorem holds substantial epistemological significance by demonstrating the power of deductive reasoning in mathematics and science. It illustrates how logical structures can yield precise knowledge of objective reality, particularly through its geometric application. Furthermore, this theorem underscores the interplay between the known and the unknown, offering a foundational example of how a well-defined system of logic—geometry—facilitates the extraction of deeper truths about the structure of reality. Through its precise formulation and experimentally demonstrable conclusions, it allows for both theoretical insight and empirical verification, bridging abstract thought and observable phenomena.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 1 (The known and the unknown). In general, the well-known Pythagorean relation holds for the known and the unknown too. It is:

$$(c^2) = (a^2) + (b^2) \quad (32)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. We begin by acknowledging Axiom 1, or the law of identity, which asserts that every entity is identical to itself. Based on this, the following equation holds:

$$+1 = +1 \quad (33)$$

Similarly, we can state:

$$X_{R,t} = X_{R,t} \quad (34)$$

Moreover, we have the following identity:

$$X_{R,t} = X_{R,t} \cdot (1 + 0) \quad (35)$$

We can further express this as:

$$X_{R,t} = X_{R,t} \cdot (1 - p(X_{R,t}) + p(X_{R,t})) \quad (36)$$

It follows that:

$$X_{R,t} = (X_{R,t} \cdot p(X_{R,t})) + (X_{R,t} \cdot (1 - p(X_{R,t}))) \quad (37)$$

From this, we derive the equation (see definition 5, p. 14):

$$X_{R,t} = E(X_{R,t}) + E(\underline{X}_{R,t}) \quad (38)$$

Multiplying equation 37 by $X_{R,t}$, we get:

$$X_{R,t} \cdot X_{R,t} = (X_{R,t} \cdot X_{R,t} \cdot p(X_{R,t})) + (X_{R,t} \cdot X_{R,t} \cdot (1 - p(X_{R,t}))) \quad (39)$$

or (see definition 5, p. 14)

$$X_{R,t} \cdot X_{R,t} = X_{R,t} \cdot E(X_{R,t}) + X_{R,t} \cdot E(\underline{X}_{R,t}) \quad (40)$$

which simplifies to (see definition 2, p. 13 and definition 5, p. 14):

$$X_{R,t}^2 = E(X_{R,t}^2) + E(\underline{X}_{R,t}^2) \quad (41)$$

Next, we define the terms as follows:

DEFINITION 24. We define:

$$c^2 = X_{R,t}^2 \quad (42)$$

DEFINITION 25. We define:

$$a^2 = E(X_{R,t}^2) \quad (43)$$

DEFINITION 26. We define:

$$b^2 = E(\underline{X}_{R,t}^2) \quad (44)$$

Finally, by combining these definitions, we obtain the well-known result:

$$(c^2) = (a^2) + (b^2) \quad (45)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Figure 3 depicts the relationship between the known and the unknown through a geometric lens.

Fig.3 Pythagorean theorem

Here:

- $X_{R,t}^2 = E(X_{R,t}^2) + E(\underline{X}_{R,t}^2)$: is the unity and the controversy of Kant's phenomena and Kant's noumena.
- $E(X_{R,t}^2)$: represents the expectation of the square of Kant's phenomena $X_{R,t}$.
- $E(\underline{X}_{R,t}^2) = X_{R,t}^2 - E(X_{R,t}^2)$: represents the expectation of the square of the other of Kant's phenomena $\underline{X}_{R,t}$.
- σ : is the height in a right triangle, called the *altitude*. The *altitude* is the line drawn from the right-angle of a right-angle triangle to the opposite side, which is the hypotenuse c .

As long as we can rightfully rely on the Pythagorean Theorem and the insights of Einstein's Special Theory of Relativity, we have a duty to emphasize the need to break free from the long-considered insurmountable limits imposed by Kant's philosophy.

The known and the unknown

The relationship between the known and the unknown are foundational to human inquiry and knowledge. The known represents established facts, theories, and experiences, forming the basis from which we explore the unknown. The unknown, in turn, drives curiosity and investigation, as it challenges the boundaries of existing knowledge, prompting the formulation of new questions and the expansion of understanding. The known is often painstakingly and gradually derived from objective reality and the unknown, step by step. This dynamic interplay between the known and unknown propels both scientific and philosophical progress.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 2 (Kant's Noumenon and Phenomenon).

$$E(X_{0,t}) = \left(1 - \frac{E(\Delta_{R,t})}{E(X_{R,t})}\right) \cdot E(X_{R,t}) \quad (46)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. Let us begin with the fundamental assumption:

$$+1 = +1 \quad (47)$$

Given this axiom, it follows that:

$$E(X_{R,t}) = E(X_{R,t}) \quad (48)$$

Here, $E(X_{R,t})$ denotes Kant's concept of phenomenon. Moreover, according to Kant, noumenon, represented as $E(X_{0,t})$, is distinct from phenomenon. Therefore, it follows that:

$$E(X_{0,t}) - E(X_{0,t}) = 0 \quad (49)$$

This implies the relationship:

$$E(X_{R,t}) = E(X_{R,t}) - E(X_{0,t}) + E(X_{0,t}) \quad (50)$$

We define the difference $E(X_{R,t}) - E(X_{0,t})$ as:

DEFINITION 27 (The difference $E(X_{R,t}) - E(X_{0,t})$).

$$E(\Delta_{R,t}) = E(X_{R,t}) - E(X_{0,t}) \quad (51)$$

In general, we have:

$$E(X_{0,t}) + E(\Delta_{R,t}) = E(X_{R,t}) \quad (52)$$

where:

- $E(X_{R,t})$: represents Kant's phenomenon.
- $E(X_{0,t})$: represents Kant's noumenon.
- $E(\Delta_{R,t})$: is the difference between the two.

Consequently, we can express the relationship as:

DEFINITION 28.

$$a^2 = E(R_{R,t}) \cdot E(\Delta_{R,t}) \quad (53)$$

and similarly:

DEFINITION 29.

$$b^2 = E(X_{0,t}) \cdot E(X_{R,t}) \quad (54)$$

and similarly:

DEFINITION 30.

$$\sigma(X_{R,t})^2 = E(X_{0,t}) \cdot E(\Delta_{R,t}) \quad (55)$$

Figure 3 illustrates these relationships in greater detail. It follows that the noumenon is given by:

$$E(X_{0,t}) = \left(1 - \frac{E(\Delta_{R,t})}{E(X_{R,t})}\right) \cdot E(X_{R,t}) \quad (56)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Figure 3 is illustrating the relationship between the known and the unknown.

Here:

- $E_{R,t} = E_{0,t} + E_{\Delta,t}$: is Kant's phenomena.
- $E_{0,t}$: is Kant's noumena.
- $E_{\Delta,t} = E_{R,t} - E_{0,t}$: is the difference between Kant's phenomena and Kant's noumena.
- σ : is the height in a right triangle, called the *altitude*. The *altitude* typically refers to the perpendicular line drawn from a vertex (usually the right-angle vertex) to the opposite side, which is the hypotenuse. Essentially, it is measure of the inner contradiction between Kant's noumena and Kant's phenomena.

Kant's Noumenon and Phenomenon

Kant distinguishes between noumenon (the thing-in-itself) and phenomenon (the thing as it appears to us). According to Kant, noumenon represents the intrinsic reality of objects, independent of our perception, while phenomenon pertains to the way these objects are perceived and understood within the framework of human cognition. Kant's epistemology set clear epistemological boundaries, positing that certain aspects of reality (noumenon) are inherently unknowable, while our knowledge is limited to the way things appear to us (phenomenon). Unfortunately, noumenon is forever beyond our reach. In contrast to Kant's position, in the context of modern physics, the distinction between noumenon and phenomenon can be compared to quantities such as rest energy, which, while calculable, may not be directly measurable with perfect precision. This interplay between exact calculation and the limitations of empirical measurement challenges the notion of absolute knowledge, suggesting a more nuanced understanding of reality that aligns with the relativity of Einstein.

Variance $\sigma (X_{R,t})^2$ of a binomial random variable

The term binomial has a very long history in science. For the first time, this term has been demonstrably used in 1557 in *The Whetstone of Witte* by Robert Recorde (see [Recorde, 1557](#)). It did not take long and Jacob Bernoulli (see [Bernoulli, 1713](#), p. 45) discovered one of the oldest known probability distributions, the binomial distribution, in his 1713 work entitled as *Ars Conjectandi*. Only view years later, in 1718, Abraham De Moivre writes about the “... the Coefficients of the Binomial ” (see [Moivre, 1718](#)). The binomial distribution is particularly useful when there are exactly two (see [Birnbaum, 1961](#), p. 417) mutually exclusive outcomes of a trial, something and its own other. In the course of further development of science, Karl Pearson presented a trial to define the standard deviation of the binomial distribution as follows:

“... the mean square error for any binomial distribution ... is identical with the value $\sqrt{npq}$ ” (see [Pearson, 1895](#), p. 351).

Pearson’s definition of the standard deviation of a Binomial distribution is more or less generally accepted, and determines a reversal of the burden of proof for anyone who still has justified doubts about the viability of such a definition. Are we even capable of assessing the truth of this Pearsonian claim?

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 3 (Expectation value I). The expectation value of a binomial random variable is given as

$$E (X_{R,t}) \equiv N \times p (X_{R,t}) \quad (57)$$

Proof by direct proof.. In general, it is (see definition 1, p. 13)

$$E (X_{R,t}) \equiv (X_{R,t}) \times p (X_{R,t}) \quad (58)$$

The expectation value $E (X_{R,t})$ of a binomial random variable is given as $N \times p (X_{R,t})$. Therefore, equation 58 changes under conditions of binomial distribution to

$$E (X_{R,t}) \equiv (X_{R,t}) \times p (X_{R,t}) \equiv N \times p (X_{R,t}) \quad (59)$$

Under condition of a binomial distribution, it is (see equation 59)

$$(X_{R,t}) \equiv N \quad (60)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 4 (Expectation value II). The expectation value of a binomial random variable squared is given as

$$E ({}_R X_t^2) \equiv N \times N \times p (X_{R,t}) \quad (61)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. It is

$$E(X_{R,t}^2) \equiv (X_{R,t}) \times (X_{R,t}) \times p(X_{R,t}) \equiv (X_{R,t}) \times E(X_{R,t}) \quad (62)$$

Based on equation 60, we obtain

$$E(X_{R,t}^2) \equiv (X_{R,t}) \times (X_{R,t}) \times p(X_{R,t}) \equiv N \times N \times p(X_{R,t}) \quad (63)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 5 (Variance of a binomial distribution). The variance of a binomial distributed random variable is given as

$$\sigma(X_{R,t})^2 = (N \times N \times p(X_{R,t})) \times (1 - (p(X_{R,t}))) \quad (64)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. It is ((see definition 12, p. 14))

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(X_{R,t})^2 &\equiv E(X_{R,t}^2) - E(X_{R,t})^2 \\ &\equiv (N \times N \times p(X_{R,t})) - (N \times p(X_{R,t}))^2 \\ &\equiv (N \times N \times p(X_{R,t})) \times (1 - (p(X_{R,t}))) \\ &\equiv (N \times p(X_{R,t})) \times N \times (1 - (p(X_{R,t}))) \\ &\equiv E(X_{R,t}) \times E(\underline{X}_{R,t}) \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Mathematical errors

The variance $\text{Var}(X)$ of a binomial distribution $X \sim \text{Bin}(n, p)$, where n is the number of trials and p is the probability of success in each trial, is given by the formula:

$$\text{Var}(X) = np(1 - p)$$

where n is number of independent trials, p : probability of success in each trial, $1 - p$: probability of failure in each trial.

The variance represents the spread or dispersion of the distribution, quantifying how much the number of successes can vary from the mean. However, as proofed before, this formula is wrong. In modern mathematics, countless errors have accumulated over time, which continue to be used without critical reflection. This represents, in part, a systematic methodological failure that requires fundamental corrective measures.

Energy E_R and time t_R

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 6 (Proof of $\ln(E_R) + \ln(T_R) = \ln(h)$). The relationship between energy and time is fundamentally governed by the equation:

$$\ln(E_R) + \ln(T_R) = \ln(h) \quad (66)$$

This equation reflects the intrinsic link between energy and time in quantum mechanics, without the presence of an intermediary. It can be shown that no third quantity exists between energy and time.

Proof by Direct Proof. We begin with the well-established Planck relation (see [Planck, 1901](#)), which connects the energy E_R of a photon to its frequency f_R :

$$E_R = h \cdot f_R \quad (67)$$

Given that the frequency f_R is the inverse of the period T_R , we can substitute:

$$f_R = \frac{1}{T_R} \quad (68)$$

Substituting this into the Planck relation gives:

$$E_R = h \cdot \frac{1}{T_R} \quad (69)$$

Thus, multiplying both sides of this equation by T_R , we obtain:

$$E_R \cdot T_R = h \quad (70)$$

This equation clearly demonstrates that the product of the energy E_R and the period T_R equals the Planck constant h .

Clarification on Period T_R and Time

To elucidate the relationship between period T_R and time, we first distinguish between the specific notion of *period* and the more general concept of *time*. The period T_R refers to the time required for one complete oscillation or cycle of a periodic phenomenon, such as a wave or vibration. This makes T_R a

precise measure of time that is relevant to systems where repetitive processes occur, like the oscillations of electromagnetic waves.

While the period is a specific time interval related to cyclical processes, *time* in its general sense can refer to any duration, continuous or discrete, in which events occur. Thus, although period T_R is a subset of the broader concept of time, it is essential in characterizing the temporal behavior of systems with regular, periodic motions.

Consider, for example, a relativistic observer R measuring the motion of a car traveling at a certain velocity. Suppose the observer measures the time it takes for the car to cover a distance of 50 meters. This duration of time corresponds to a specific event—the completion of a finite displacement over a given path. While this duration is not strictly periodic, we can still relate this measurement to the notion of period T_R if the motion of the car repeats, as in circular or oscillatory motion.

In the context of periodic motion, the period T_R would represent the time required for the car to return to its initial position after one full cycle of travel. If the car's motion were cyclical, the time T_R would correspond to the period of that cycle. Thus, in both periodic and non-periodic contexts, time intervals can be seen as specific realizations of broader temporal phenomena, and the period T_R serves as a defining measure of cyclical processes.

Refined Insight on T_R and Velocity Example

For a more direct analogy, consider a wave traveling along a medium. The velocity of the wave corresponds to the distance traveled per unit time, just as the car's velocity is distance over time. The period T_R of the wave represents the time it takes for one complete cycle (e.g., the passage of one wavelength). Similarly, in the car analogy, if the motion is periodic (e.g., the car completes a loop), T_R would denote the time required for one complete trip around the loop.

Thus, period T_R provides a structured and repeating form of time measurement, whereas general time measurements, like the car's travel time over a straight distance, can be treated as single intervals without periodicity.

We regard the period T_R as time itself, but as a concrete form of time.

Logarithmic Transformation and Further Insights

Taking the natural logarithm of both sides of the equation provides deeper insight into the proportional relationship:

$$\ln(E_R \cdot T_R) = \ln(h) \quad (71)$$

In the field of mathematical analysis, logarithmic properties are fundamental tools used to simplify and manipulate expressions involving products, quotients, and powers. One such property is the logarithm of a product, which is commonly used in various branches of mathematics, including calculus, algebra, and number theory.

The Logarithm of a Product

The logarithm of a product can be expressed as the sum of the logarithms of the individual factors. Formally, for any positive real numbers A and B , the following rule holds:

$$\ln(A \cdot B) = \ln(A) + \ln(B) \quad (72)$$

Planck's constant h is treated as a constant. This implies that there is no third option (*tertium non datur*) between energy E_R and time T_R , reinforcing the absence of an intermediary between these two. The more energy, the less time, the more time the less energy. In general, it is

$$\ln(E_R) + \ln(T_R) = \ln(h) \quad (73)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The conclusion is in line with the principle of *tertium non datur* (no third possibility): energy and time are mutually interdependent, each defining and limiting the other, yet they exclude any intermediary. Nonetheless, Energy passes over into time and vice versa, time passes over into energy.

The relationship between energy and time appears to be defined by a strict opposition, leaving no room for indeterminacy or vagueness. This opposition is foundational to understanding the nature of their interdependence, where energy and time form two distinct but interconnected aspects of reality. The distinction between these two concepts mirrors the philosophical principle of identity and difference, with each opposing term playing a critical role in defining the other. Objective reality, as constituted by such opposites, introduces a compelling line of reasoning. If one aspect, such as energy, cannot be measured or fully known, its counterpart—time—must necessarily be accessible, and vice versa. This complementary nature allows for decisive conclusions in cases where direct measurement or demonstration of one concept is impossible, suggesting a form of balance or symmetry between these opposing terms.

The interplay between energy and time as opposites, is a natural foundation of the philosophical concept of the Law of Excluded Middle. This principle, deeply embedded in the structure of classical logic, suggests that the absence of one pole necessitates the presence of the other, enabling a comprehensive understanding even in the absence of complete direct measurement. Historically, this law traces its origins back to Aristotle, who formulated it as a principle of metaphysical and logical reasoning in his *Metaphysics*. Aristotle's Law of Excluded Middle posits that for any proposition, either it is true or

its negation is true—there is no middle ground between the two. Equation 73 can be rearranged as

$$\frac{\ln(E_R)}{\ln(h)} + \frac{\ln(T_R)}{\ln(h)} = \frac{\ln(h)}{\ln(h)} = +1 \quad (74)$$

Time is determined by energy as:

$$\ln(T_R) = \ln(h) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\ln(E_R)}{\ln(h)}\right) \quad (75)$$

Energy is determined by time as:

$$\ln(E_R) = \ln(h) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\ln(T_R)}{\ln(h)}\right) \quad (76)$$

Particle Wave Duality

The relationship between particle and wave can be viewed as a dynamic unity of opposites, where both are reconciled through their mutual interaction. Opposites are not merely contradictory but exist in a relationship where each embodies aspects of its own other. Thus, particles, which appear discrete and localized, and waves, which are continuous and spread-out, come together in quantum mechanics as complementary aspects of a deeper, unified reality. This unity of contradiction reaches equilibrium not through static opposition but through the dynamic process of becoming and transformation, embodying a synthesis that reflects the evolution of nature itself.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 7 (Particle Wave Duality).

The duality between the particle and the wave is determined by the relationship:

$$\frac{(E_{0,t})^2}{(E_{R,t})^2} + \frac{(E_{W,t})^2}{(E_{R,t})^2} = 1 \quad (77)$$

Where:

- $E_{0,t} = (m_{0,t} \cdot c^2)$: Represents the rest energy of an object as measured by the co-moving observer 0.
- $E_{R,t} = (m_{R,t} \cdot c^2)$: Represents the total or relativistic energy of an object as measured by the relativistic observer R .
- $E_{W,t} = (m_{R,t} \cdot v \cdot c)$: Is the energy of the electromagnetic wave as measured by the relativistic observer R . For mass-less particles, the relationship is given by $E_{W,t} = E_{R,t}$ because $E_{0,t} = 0$

Proof by Direct Proof. We begin with the axiom that:

$$+1 = +1 \quad (78)$$

This elementary truth implies that:

$$m_{0,t} = m_{0,t} \quad (79)$$

According to Einstein's theory of relativity, this equality is equivalent to the following relation:

$$m_{0,t} = \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot m_{R,t} \quad (80)$$

We now rearrange this equation:

$$\frac{m_{0,t}}{m_{R,t}} = \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \quad (81)$$

Squaring both sides results in the equation:

$$\frac{m_{0,t}^2}{m_{R,t}^2} = 1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \quad (82)$$

Rearranging this expression slightly gives:

$$\frac{m_{0,t}^2}{m_{R,t}^2} + \frac{v^2}{c^2} = 1 \quad (83)$$

We extend both the numerator and denominator:

$$\frac{m_{0,t}^2 \cdot c^2 \cdot c^2}{m_{R,t}^2 \cdot c^2 \cdot c^2} + \frac{v^2 \cdot m_{R,t}^2 \cdot c^2}{c^2 \cdot m_{R,t}^2 \cdot c^2} = 1 \quad (84)$$

This leads to:

$$\frac{(m_{0,t} \cdot c^2) \cdot (m_{0,t} \cdot c^2)}{(m_{R,t} \cdot c^2) \cdot (m_{R,t} \cdot c^2)} + \frac{(m_{R,t}^2 \cdot v^2) \cdot (c^2)}{(m_{R,t} \cdot c^2) \cdot (m_{R,t} \cdot c^2)} = 1 \quad (85)$$

Where:

- $m_{0,t}$: Represents the rest mass of an object as measured by a co-moving observer 0.
- $m_{R,t}$: Represents the total or relativistic mass of an object as measured by a relativistic observer R .
- v : Denotes the relative velocity between the co-moving observer and the stationary observer.
- c : Is the speed of light in vacuum.

The equation simplifies, reflecting the insights of special relativity:

$$\frac{(m_{0,t} \cdot c^2) \cdot (m_{0,t} \cdot c^2)}{(m_{R,t} \cdot c^2) \cdot (m_{R,t} \cdot c^2)} + \frac{(m_{R,t}^2 \cdot v^2) \cdot (c^2)}{(m_{R,t} \cdot c^2) \cdot (m_{R,t} \cdot c^2)} = 1 \quad (86)$$

This equation further simplifies:

$$\frac{(E_{0,t})^2}{(E_{R,t})^2} + \frac{(m_{R,t} \cdot v)^2 \cdot (c^2)}{(E_{R,t})^2} = 1 \quad (87)$$

Where:

- $E_{0,t} = (m_{0,t} \cdot c^2)$: Represents the rest energy of an object as measured by the co-moving observer 0.
- $E_{R,t} = (m_{R,t} \cdot c^2)$: Represents the total or relativistic energy of an object as measured by the relativistic observer R .

- v : Denotes the relative velocity between the co-moving observer and the stationary observer.
- c : Is the speed of light in vacuum.

Relativistic momentum is defined as $p_{R,t} = (m_{R,t} \cdot v)$. This simplifies the equation:

$$\frac{(E_{0,t})^2}{(E_{R,t})^2} + \frac{(p_{R,t})^2 \cdot (c^2)}{(E_{R,t})^2} = 1 \quad (88)$$

Further simplification yields:

$$\frac{(E_{0,t})^2}{(E_{R,t})^2} + \frac{(p_{R,t} \cdot c)^2}{(E_{R,t})^2} = 1 \quad (89)$$

Particle-wave duality is a fundamental property of nature where all particles exhibit both particle-like and wave-like behaviour at the same time. In a wave, the presence of a particle can be discerned, and within a particle, wave-like properties can be observed. The dual nature of matter and energy has been captured mathematically by de Broglie's wavelength too. As known, it is well-established that the energy of an electromagnetic wave is determined by $E_{W,t} = (p_{R,t} \cdot c)$, where $E_{W,t}$ represents the energy of the electromagnetic wave. The unity and the struggle between a particle and a wave then becomes:

$$\frac{(E_{0,t})^2}{(E_{R,t})^2} + \frac{(E_{W,t})^2}{(E_{R,t})^2} = 1 \quad (90)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The unity and struggle between particle and wave culminates in the conceptual and mathematical framework of quantum mechanics, specifically in Equation 90, which reconciles these seemingly contradictory aspects of nature. This unity of opposites represents a natural process where both particle and wave embody mutually dependent qualities: particles are discrete and localized, while waves are continuous and extended. Neither can exist in isolation without the other, and their relationship reflects the deep tension between individuality and totality. This struggle is not static but dynamic, continuously unfolding through the quantum wave function, which describes the probabilistic nature of particles manifesting as waves. Thus, the duality of particle and wave is resolved not through separation but through the unity of both where each finds its completeness in its own other within the evolving structure of objective reality.

Relativistic potential energy and relativistic kinetic energy I

Relativistic potential energy and relativistic kinetic energy are two fundamental forms of mechanical energy that are interrelated within the framework of classical mechanics. Potential energy, often associated with the position or configuration of an object, can be converted into kinetic energy, which is the energy of motion, as the object moves or changes state. The principle of conservation of energy states that in a closed system, the total mechanical energy—comprising both potential and kinetic energy—remains constant, illustrating how these forms of energy can transform into one another without loss.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 8 (Relativistic potential energy and relativistic kinetic energy). The relationship between relativistic potential energy and relativistic kinetic energy is foundational to understanding the dynamics of objects under relativistic conditions. The relationship between the relativistic potential energy and the relativistic kinetic energy is determined by the equation:

$$(E_{RP,t}) + (E_{RK,t}) = (E_{R,t}) \quad (91)$$

Here:

- $E_{RP,t} = \left(\left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot E_{0,t} \right)$: Represents the relativistic potential energy of an object.
- $E_{RK,t} = (m_{R,t} \cdot v^2)$: Represents the relativistic kinetic energy of an object as measured by the relativistic observer R .
- $E_{R,t} = (m_{R,t} \cdot c^2)$: Represents the total or relativistic energy of an object as measured by the relativistic observer R .

Proof by Direct Proof. Axiomatically, the following statement holds:

$$+1 = +1 \quad (92)$$

By this same reasoning, the following relationship is equally valid:

$$\frac{(E_{0,t})^2}{(E_{R,t})^2} + \frac{(E_{W,t})^2}{(E_{R,t})^2} = 1 \quad (93)$$

Here:

- $E_{0,t} = (m_{0,t} \cdot c^2)$: Represents the rest energy of an object as measured by the co-moving observer 0 .
- $E_{R,t} = (m_{R,t} \cdot c^2)$: Represents the total or relativistic energy of an object as measured by the relativistic observer R .

- $E_{W,t} = (m_{R,t} \cdot v \cdot c)$: Is the energy of the electromagnetic wave as measured by the relativistic observer R . For massless particles, the relationship simplifies to $E_{W,t} = E_{R,t}$ as $E_{0,t} = 0$.

LEMMA 1. The relativistic potential energy, denoted as $E_{RP,t}$, is given by:

$$E_{RP,t} = \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot E_{0,t} \quad (94)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. Let us assume:

$$X \cdot (E_{R,t}) = (E_{0,t})^2 \quad (95)$$

From this, it follows that:

$$X = \frac{(E_{0,t})^2}{(E_{R,t})} = \frac{(E_{R,t}) \cdot \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot E_{0,t}}{(E_{R,t})} = \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \cdot E_{0,t} \right) = E_{EP,t} \quad (96)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Rewriting the original equation, we obtain:

$$\frac{\left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \cdot E_{0,t} \right) \cdot E_{R,t}}{(E_{R,t})^2} + \frac{(E_{W,t})^2}{(E_{R,t})^2} = 1 \quad (97)$$

This simplifies to:

$$\frac{\left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \cdot E_{0,t} \right)}{(E_{R,t})} + \frac{(E_{W,t})^2}{(E_{R,t})^2} = 1 \quad (98)$$

LEMMA 2. The relativistic kinetic energy denoted as $E_{RK,t}$, is given by:

$$E_{RK,t} = m_{R,t} \cdot v^2 \quad (99)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. Assume that:

$$Y \cdot (E_{R,t}) = (E_{W,t})^2 \quad (100)$$

Thus, we have:

$$Y = \frac{(E_{W,t})^2}{(E_{R,t})} = \frac{m_{R,t}^2 \cdot v^2 \cdot c^2}{m_{R,t} \cdot c^2} = m_{R,t} \cdot v^2 = E_{RK,t} \quad (101)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The original equation then becomes:

$$\frac{\left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \cdot E_{0,t}\right)}{(E_{R,t})} + \frac{(E_{W,t}) \cdot (E_{RK,t})}{(E_{R,t})^2} = 1 \quad (102)$$

This simplifies to:

$$\frac{(E_{RP,t})}{(E_{R,t})} + \frac{(E_{RK,t})}{(E_{R,t})} = 1 \quad (103)$$

In general, the relationship holds:

$$(E_{RP,t}) + (E_{RK,t}) = (E_{R,t}) \quad (104)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Relativistic Potential Energy and Relativistic Kinetic Energy II

The time-dependent Schrödinger equation (see [Schrödinger, Erwin Rudolf Josef Alexander, 1926](#); [Born, 1926](#)) characterizes the dynamical evolution of a quantum mechanical system by describing how the wave function $\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ changes with time. It links the system's energy, represented by the Hamiltonian operator $\hat{H}$, to the temporal variation of the wave function. This equation is crucial for tracking the system's time evolution and comprehending the probabilistic nature of quantum mechanics.

The time-independent Schrödinger equation is given by:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \hat{H} \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (105)$$

Here:

- i is the imaginary unit,
- $\hbar$ is the reduced Planck constant ($\hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi}$),
- $\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ represents the wave function of the system, which depends on spatial coordinates $\mathbf{r}$ and time t ,
- $\hat{H}$ denotes the Hamiltonian operator of the system, encapsulating the total energy of the system.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 9. The relativistic (see [Klein, 1926](#); [Barukčić, 2013](#)) Schrödinger equation for relativistic potential energy (i. e. particle) and relativistic kinetic energy (i.e. wave) is expressed as:

$$\left(\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right) \cdot \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \right) + \left(\left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right) \cdot \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \right) = \hat{H} \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (106)$$

This equation illustrates the distribution of total energy into two distinct terms. The first term accounts for the contribution from relativistic potential energy component, weighted by the factor $\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)$, while the second term describes the influence of the relativistic kinetic energy component, scaled by the relative velocity squared $\left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)$. The sum of these two contributions is equal to the total Hamiltonian acting on the wave function $\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$.

Proof by Direct Proof. We begin with the fundamental identity:

$$1 = 1 \quad (107)$$

which serves as a basic axiom. This can be restated as:

$$1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} + \frac{v^2}{c^2} = 1, \quad (108)$$

demonstrating that the sum of the distinct parts, influenced by the velocity term, indeed equals unity. By multiplying both sides by $\hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$, we get:

$$\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \cdot (\hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)) + \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \cdot (\hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)) = \hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (109)$$

This equation confirms that the sum of the relativistic potential energy and relativistic kinetic energy contributions, when weighted appropriately by their respective factors, reproduces the total energy operator acting on the wave function.

Thus, the relativistic Schrödinger equation for relativistic potential energy and relativistic kinetic energy simplifies to:

$$\left(\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \cdot \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t}\right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t)\right) + \left(\left(\frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \cdot \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t}\right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t)\right) = \hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (110)$$

emphasizing that both relativistic potential energy $E_{RP,t}$ and relativistic kinetic energy $E_{RK,t}$ components are integral parts of the overall relativistic energy description.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The opposition between particle and wave has been a fundamental issue in science with profound implications for our understanding of both matter and energy and challenges our classical intuitions about the nature of reality. The debate primarily revolves around the dual nature of subatomic entities, such as electrons, which exhibit properties of both particles and waves depending on the context.

Quantum mechanics, particularly through the double-slit experiment, has shown that particles like electrons can display wave-like interference patterns when not observed, suggesting that they exist in a superposition of states. However, when measured, these same entities behave like discrete particles. This wave-particle duality poses far-reaching questions about the nature of observation and the role of the observer in determining the state of physical systems.

Niels Bohr's principle of complementarity offers one resolution to this contradiction. It posits that particle and wave descriptions are mutually exclusive yet complementary perspectives of the same reality. Bohr argued that we must choose one framework depending on the experimental setup, as both cannot be applied simultaneously. In contrast, the realist interpretation, such as Einstein's, insisted that underlying particles exist independently of observation and that wave properties emerge from our lack of knowledge about their precise states.

The debate extends into various considerations: Does the wave function represent a real, physical entity, or is it merely a tool for predicting probabilities? The Copenhagen interpretation, favoring the latter, contends that the wave function is a complete description of a system's potential states. In contrast, alternative interpretations like Bohmian mechanics advocate for a deterministic particle trajectory, guided by a pilot wave.

Ultimately, the particle-wave duality challenges the classical dichotomy of either-or frameworks and invites us to reconsider how we conceptualize the nature of existence itself, blurring the lines between matter and energy, and between reality and potentiality.

Ordinary Energy and Electromagnetic Wave Energy

Einstein defined the relationship between ordinary matter and electromagnetic field ex negativo:

“Wir unterscheiden im folgenden zwischen ‘Gravitationsfeld’ und ‘Materie’, in dem Sinne, daß **alles außer dem Gravitationsfeld als ‘Materie’ bezeichnet** wird, also nicht nur die ‘Materie’ im üblichen Sinne, sondern auch das elektromagnetische Feld. ”

(Einstein, 1916, p. 802/803)

Einstein’s position translated into English: ‘We distinguish in the following between ‘gravitational field’ and ‘matter’ in the sense that **everything except the gravitational field is referred to as ‘matter’**, not only matter in the usual sense, but also the electromagnetic field.’ In other words, the demarcation delineated by Einstein elucidates all entities beyond the gravitational field are encompassed under the term ‘matter’ whereby ‘matter’ itself is categorized into the **‘matter’ in the usual sense** and into **the electromagnetic field**.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 10. The relativistic Schrödinger equation for ordinary energy and electromagnetic wave energy is formulated as follows:

$$\left(\left(1 - \frac{v}{c} \right) \cdot \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \right) + \left(\left(\frac{v}{c} \right) \cdot \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \right) = \hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (111)$$

This equation represents the division of the total energy contribution into the ordinary energy component and the remaining electromagnetic energy component.

Proof by Direct Proof. Starting with Axiom 1, which states:

$$1 = 1 \quad (112)$$

we recognize the equality

$$1 - \frac{v}{c} + \frac{v}{c} = 1 \quad (113)$$

as trivially true. Multiplying both sides of the equation by $\hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$, we obtain:

$$\left(1 - \frac{v}{c} \right) \cdot \left(\hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \right) + \left(\frac{v}{c} \right) \cdot \left(\hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \right) = \hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (114)$$

This confirms that the total energy operator acting on the wave function is equal to the sum of its components, corresponding to ordinary energy and electromagnetic wave energy. Thus, the relativistic Schrödinger equation for ordinary energy and electromagnetic wave energy simplifies to:

$$\left(1 - \frac{v}{c} \right) \cdot \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) + \left(\frac{v}{c} \right) \cdot \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (115)$$

showing that the contributions from ordinary energy and electromagnetic wave energy are indeed complementary components of the total energy in a relativistic framework.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Rest Energy and Delta Energy

Physically, the concept of rest energy revolutionizes the classical view by suggesting that mass itself is a concentrated form of energy, irrespective of motion. This challenges traditional notions where energy was typically associated only with kinetic and potential forms. The delta energy, in contrast, contextualizes how motion and external interactions contribute to the object's total energy beyond its intrinsic rest energy.

Theoretically, this distinction suggests a layered reality where energy exists in multiple forms—both intrinsic and relational. It also draws a parallel to other notions, where objects possess properties independently of observation or external influences. This perspective invites reconsideration of energy and matter as interdependent entities, fundamentally linked by the fabric of spacetime.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 11. The relativistic Schrödinger equation for rest energy and delta energy can be formulated as follows:

$$\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \right) \right) + \left(\left(\left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \right) \right) = \hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (116)$$

The first term on the left side of the equation represents the contribution of rest energy, which is the energy of a particle at rest as perceived by an observer in the same inertial frame. The second term represents the delta energy, capturing the deviation from rest energy due to relative motion.

Proof by Direct Proof. We start with the trivial identity:

$$+1 = +1 \quad (117)$$

Given this, it logically follows that:

$$+1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} + \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = +1 \quad (118)$$

This equality holds as we add and subtract the same term. Now, by multiplying both sides of the equation by $\hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$, we obtain:

$$\left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot (\hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)) + \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot (\hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)) = \hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (119)$$

This confirms that the sum of the rest energy and delta energy components yields the total relativistic energy. Therefore, the relativistic Schrödinger equation for rest energy and delta energy is:

$$\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \right) \right) + \left(\left(\left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right) \cdot \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \right) \right) = \hat{H}\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (120)$$

This formulation elegantly encapsulates the interplay between rest energy and delta energy, emphasizing their combined effect in determining the total energy of the system.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Kant's Ding an sich (thing-in-itself) refers to the reality that exists independently of our perception. According to Kant, we can never know the true nature of this reality directly; we only experience phenomena, which are filtered through the structures of our perception and cognition. If we consider rest energy as the physical counterpart of the thing-in-itself, it implies that rest energy is an intrinsic property of matter, existing independently of our observation, akin to Kant's metaphysical concept.

Rest energy, expressed by Einstein's famous equation $E_{0,t} = m_{0,t}c^2$, is the energy possessed by an object due to its mass alone, without any motion or external influences. It is a fundamental, immutable property of matter, reflecting a deeper reality that persists regardless of changes in external conditions or frames of reference. This suggests that rest energy represents a kind of noumenal reality, which remains constant and unaffected by the phenomenal world of appearances.

The connection between rest energy and Kant's thing-in-itself highlights a philosophical convergence between metaphysics and physics, where rest energy serves as a bridge between observable phenomena and an underlying, unknowable reality. In this view, rest energy is not just a measure of an object's potential to do work but a symbol of its fundamental existence, unaffected by how it is perceived or measured. This interpretation provides a profound insight into the nature of reality, suggesting that, while we interact with the world through its manifestations (phenomena), there exists an indestructible core to objects, much like the elusive Ding an sich.

This analogy between Kantian philosophy and modern physics invites further exploration, as it could offer a framework for understanding the limits of scientific knowledge and the nature of existence itself. It also raises intriguing questions about the relationship between consciousness and the physical world, potentially enriching both philosophical discourse and scientific inquiry.

Rest energy can be determined to an extraordinarily high degree of accuracy in experimental physics, which enables scientists to make precise predictions and validations of theoretical models. Rest energy is precisely given by Einstein's equation $E_{0,t} = m_{0,t}c^2$, which expresses the intrinsic energy of an object at rest due to its mass. This suggests that rest energy serves as a kind of physical counterpart to Kant's metaphysical concept, representing a fundamental reality of objects that remains constant and unobservable in itself, much like the thing-in-itself.

Kant posited that the noumenon, or thing-in-itself, is an unknowable reality beyond human experience and perception. However, Einstein's theory of relativity challenges much of Kant's concept of the noumenon.

Physical Content of the Stress-Energy Tensor $\frac{8\pi\gamma}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}$

The stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ represents the distribution of energy, momentum, and stress in a physical system. This tensor is crucial for understanding how energy and momentum propagate through space and time, especially within the framework of General Relativity, where it serves as the source term in Einstein's field equations. These equations link the geometry of spacetime to the matter and energy it contains. Specifically, the components of $T_{\mu\nu}$ represent various physical quantities, including energy density, momentum density, and stress (encompassing pressure and shear). The energy density $\frac{E_{R,t}}{V_{R,t}}$ is one of the key quantities that the stress-energy tensor can describe:

$$\text{Energy Density} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{V_{R,t}} \quad (121)$$

This definition will be further expanded and used in the derivations below.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 12 (Physical Content of the Stress-Energy Tensor $\frac{8\pi\gamma}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}$).

$$\text{Energy Density} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{V_{R,t}} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{W_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{F_{R,t} \cdot s}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{F_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{F_{R,t}}{A_{R,t}} = p_{\text{pressure},t} \quad (122)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. We begin with an axiom:

$$+1 = +1 \quad (123)$$

This fundamental identity holds universally. By analogy, we state that:

$$\text{Energy Density} = \text{Energy Density} \quad (124)$$

The energy density is well-known to be defined as the energy $E_{R,t}$ per unit volume $V_{R,t}$, which can be written as:

$$\text{Energy Density} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{V_{R,t}} \quad (125)$$

The volume $V_{R,t}$ can be expressed as the product of three spatial dimensions $s_{R,t}$:

$$V_{R,t} = s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \quad (126)$$

Thus, the expression for energy density becomes:

$$\text{Energy Density} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} \quad (127)$$

Next, we make use of the fact that energy $E_{R,t}$ and work $W_{R,t}$ are conceptually identical in this context. Therefore, we substitute energy with work:

$$E_{R,t} = W_{R,t} \quad (128)$$

Equation before becomes

$$\text{Energy Density} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{V_{R,t}} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{W_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} \quad (129)$$

Work $W_{R,t}$ is defined as the product of the force $F_{R,t}$ and displacement $s_{R,t}$:

$$W_{R,t} = F_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \quad (130)$$

where

- $W_{R,t}$: is work.
- $F_{R,t}$: is the applied force.
- $s_{R,t}$: the displacement in the direction of the force.

Inserting this into the expression for energy density, we get:

$$\text{Energy Density} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{V_{R,t}} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{W_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{F_{R,t} \cdot s}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} \quad (131)$$

This can be simplified to:

$$\text{Energy Density} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{V_{R,t}} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{W_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{F_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} \quad (132)$$

Recognizing that the product $s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}$ represents the area $A_{R,t}$, or

$$A_{R,t} = s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \quad (133)$$

the expression before becomes:

$$\text{Energy Density} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{V_{R,t}} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{W_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{F_{R,t} \cdot s}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{F_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{F_{R,t}}{A_{R,t}} \quad (134)$$

It is known that pressure $p_{\text{pressure},t}$ is defined as the force per unit area:

$$p_{\text{pressure},t} = \frac{F_{R,t}}{A_{R,t}} \quad (135)$$

This concludes the derivation, demonstrating that the energy density of the system can be expressed as the pressure under the appropriate conditions as:

$$\text{Energy Density} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{V_{R,t}} = \frac{E_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{W_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{F_{R,t} \cdot s}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{F_{R,t}}{s_{R,t} \cdot s_{R,t}} = \frac{F_{R,t}}{A_{R,t}} = p_{\text{pressure},t} \quad (136)$$

where

-
- $E_{R,t}$: Energy, measured in joules (J), represents the total energy contained within a system or object.
 - $V_{R,t}$: Volume, measured in cubic meters (m^3), represents the spatial extent within which the total energy $E_{R,t}$ is distributed.
 - $W_{R,t}$: Work, also measured in joules (J), is the transfer of energy by mechanical means. Energy and work are often considered identical.
 - $F_{R,t}$: Force, measured in newtons (N), is the interaction that changes the motion of an object.
 - $s_{R,t}$: Length, measured in meters (m), represents a distance in space.
 - $A_{R,t}$: Area, measured in square meters (m^2), represents the extent of a surface.
 - $p_{\text{pressure},t}$: Pressure, measured in pascals (Pa), is the force per unit area exerted on a surface.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The Einstein's field equations and Schrödinger equation

Directly translating general relativity into a Schrödinger-like framework involves significant theoretical challenges, including reconciling the classical description of spacetime with quantum mechanics. However, describing Einstein's field equations in a Schrödinger-like form could provide some help for exploring the analogies between quantum mechanics and general relativity. It might offer insights into how gravitational fields could be treated in a quantum mechanical framework. In general, such a successful reformulation might help bridge gaps between classical gravity and quantum theory, providing a new perspective on the quest for a unified theory of quantum gravity.

What are the units of the quantities in the Einstein field equation?

To address the units of the various quantities in the Einstein field equations (EFE), let's carefully analyze each term in the equation:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R + g_{\mu\nu}\Lambda = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (137)$$

- **Ricci Curvature Tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$:**

The Ricci curvature tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ is derived from the Riemann curvature tensor, which involves second derivatives of the metric tensor. Each derivative introduces a factor of m^{-1} (inverse length), so the Ricci tensor, being a contraction of the Riemann tensor, has units of m^{-2} . This unit corresponds to the curvature of spacetime.

- **Scalar Curvature R :**

The scalar curvature R is a trace of the Ricci tensor, which involves summing the diagonal elements of $R_{\mu\nu}$. Since contraction does not alter the units, R also has units of m^{-2} , consistent with those of the Ricci tensor.

- **Metric Tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$:**

The metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ is a dimensionless quantity. It serves as a scaling factor that relates distances in curved spacetime but does not have physical units.

- **Cosmological Constant Λ :**

The cosmological constant Λ appears in the equation as a term multiplied by the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. To ensure dimensional consistency with the Ricci curvature tensor and the scalar curvature, Λ must have units of m^{-2} . This ensures that the term $g_{\mu\nu}\Lambda$ has the same units as $R_{\mu\nu}$ and $\frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R$.

- **Stress-Energy Tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$:**

The stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ represents energy density in spacetime, which has units of J/m^3 . Since J (joule) is equivalent to $kg \cdot m^2/s^2$, the units J/m^3 can be expressed as $kg \cdot m^{-1} \cdot s^{-2}$. However, $T_{\mu\nu}$ can also be interpreted as pressure, which has units of N/m^2 . Since N (newton) is

$kg \cdot m \cdot s^{-2}$, the units N/m^2 are also equivalent to $kg \cdot m^{-1} \cdot s^{-2}$. To match the units, it is necessary to multiply $T_{\mu\nu}$ with of $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$. Let's examine the units of the factor $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}$. Thus,

$$\frac{G}{c^4} = \frac{m^3 \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot s^{-2}}{(m/s)^4} = \frac{\frac{m^3}{kg \cdot s^2}}{\frac{m^4}{s^4}} = \frac{m^3 \cdot s^4}{kg \cdot s^2 \cdot m^4} = \frac{s^2}{kg \cdot m} = m^{-1} \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot s^2$$

In summary:

- $R_{\mu\nu}$ and R both have units of m^{-2} .
- $g_{\mu\nu}$ is dimensionless.
- Λ has units of m^{-2} .
- $T_{\mu\nu}$ has units of J/m^3 or N/m^2 . Thus, $T_{\mu\nu}$ having units of J/m^3 or N/m^2 does not match m^{-2} directly, but when multiplied by the factor $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}$, the units of $T_{\mu\nu}$ converts to a consistent unit of m^{-2} .

In other words, the units on both sides of the Einstein field equations

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R + g_{\mu\nu}\Lambda = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (138)$$

are consistent, ensuring the dimensional coherence of the equation.

To understand the significance of the term $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}$ in General Relativity, we need to examine the units and physical interpretation of this expression more closely.

Units and Meaning

The term $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}$ appears in the Einstein field equations:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R + g_{\mu\nu}\Lambda = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}$$

Here are the units for each component:

- **Gravitational Constant G :**

$$G \text{ has units of: } \frac{m^3}{kg \cdot s^2} = m^3 \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot s^{-2}. \quad (139)$$

- **Speed of Light c :**

$$c \text{ has units of: } \frac{m}{s} = m \cdot s^{-1}. \quad (140)$$

- **Stress-Energy Tensor** $T_{\mu\nu}$: $T_{\mu\nu}$ has units of $\frac{\text{Energy}}{\text{Volume}}$ or J/m^3 or N/m^2 , which is equivalent to :

$$\frac{J}{m^3} = \frac{N \cdot m}{m^3} = \frac{N}{m^2} = \frac{kg \cdot m^2}{s^2 \cdot m^3} = \frac{kg}{s^2 \cdot m} \quad (141)$$

- **Units of** $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}$:

$$\frac{G}{c^4} = \frac{m^3 \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot s^{-2}}{(m/s)^4} = \frac{\frac{m^3}{kg \cdot s^2}}{\frac{m^4}{s^4}} = \frac{m^3 \cdot s^4}{kg \cdot s^2 \cdot m^4} = m^{-1} \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot s^2 = \frac{s^2}{kg \cdot m} \quad (142)$$

- **Therefore, the units of** $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$ **are::**

$$\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{s^2}{kg \cdot m} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{kg}{s^2 \cdot m} \right) = \frac{1}{m^2} = m^{-2} \quad (143)$$

Physical Meaning

The term $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$ on the right-hand side of the Einstein field equations describes the relationship between the distribution of energy and momentum in the space-time continuum and the curvature of space-time. The units of $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$ are m^{-2} , which describes the curvature of space-time.

In summary:

- $T_{\mu\nu}$ represents the energy and momentum density of a system, expressed in units such as J/m^3 or N/m^2 .
- **The term** $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$ **has units of** m^{-2} , which corresponds to the unit of space-time curvature.

Thus, the physical significance of the term $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$ is clear: it represents the contribution of energy and momentum density to the curvature of space-time.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 13 (The Einstein's field equations and Schrödinger equation). The Einstein's field equations in a Schrödinger-like form are given as:

$$\left(\frac{V_{R,t} \cdot c^4}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G} \cdot \left(R - \frac{R \cdot D}{2} \right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \right) + \left(\frac{V_{R,t} \cdot c^4}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G} \cdot (\Lambda \cdot D) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \right) = \hat{H} \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (144)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. We begin with an axiom:

$$+1 = +1 \quad (145)$$

This fundamental identity holds universally. By analogy, we state that:

$$\left(\frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4}\right) \cdot T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4}\right) \cdot T_{\mu\nu} \quad (146)$$

To derive the energy density field equation from the Einstein's field equations, we start with the Einstein field equations as:

$$(R_{\mu\nu}) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \cdot g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4}\right) \cdot T_{\mu\nu} \quad (147)$$

We rearrange this equation to solve for the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$:

$$\left(\frac{c^4}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}\right) \cdot \left((R_{\mu\nu}) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \cdot g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu})\right) = T_{\mu\nu} \quad (148)$$

Next, we multiply this equation by a certain volume $V_{R,t}$:

$$V_{R,t} \cdot \left(\frac{c^4}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}\right) \cdot \left((R_{\mu\nu}) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \cdot g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu})\right) = V_{R,t} \cdot T_{\mu\nu} \quad (149)$$

Taking the trace of this equation, it is

$$V_{R,t} \cdot \left(\frac{c^4}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}\right) \cdot \left((R_{\mu\nu} \cdot g^{\mu\nu}) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \cdot g_{\mu\nu} \cdot g^{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu} \cdot g^{\mu\nu})\right) = V_{R,t} \cdot T_{\mu\nu} \cdot g^{\mu\nu} \quad (150)$$

while the certain volume $V_{R,t}$ is a scalar. Equation before simplifies to:

$$V_{R,t} \cdot \left(\frac{c^4}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}\right) \cdot \left((R) - \left(\frac{R \cdot D}{2}\right) + (\Lambda \cdot D)\right) = V_{R,t} \cdot T \quad (151)$$

where T is Laue's scalar (see [Laue, 1911](#); [von Laue, 1918](#)). Whether the following assumption can be considered universally valid may be subject to further research. Under the assumption that there exist circumstances where the condition

$$E_{R,t} = V_{R,t} \cdot T = \hat{H} \quad (152)$$

can be taken as given, the following result immediately follows. The previously stated equation transforms as follows:

$$\left(\frac{V_{R,t} \cdot c^4}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G} \cdot \left(R - \frac{R \cdot D}{2}\right)\right) + \left(\frac{V_{R,t} \cdot c^4}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G} \cdot (\Lambda \cdot D)\right) = V_{R,t} \cdot T = E_{R,t} = \hat{H} \quad (153)$$

Multiplying through by the wave function $\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$, we obtain the relativistic time-dependent Schrodinger's equation of the Einstein's field equation as:

$$\left(\frac{V_{R,t} \cdot c^4}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G} \cdot \left(R - \frac{R \cdot D}{2}\right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t)\right) + \left(\frac{V_{R,t} \cdot c^4}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G} \cdot (\Lambda \cdot D) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t)\right) = \hat{H} \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (154)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Quantum mechanics and Einstein's general theory offer fundamentally different views of the universe. General relativity describes gravity as the curvature of spacetime caused by mass and energy, providing a macroscopic understanding of the universe's structure and dynamics. It works exceptionally well at large scales, such as those involving stars, galaxies, and the entire cosmos. In contrast, quantum mechanics governs the behavior of particles at the smallest scales, where uncertainties and probabilistic outcomes dominate. This framework successfully describes the interactions of particles and forces, but its principles seem to contradict the smooth, continuous nature of spacetime envisioned by relativity.

The challenge of reconciling these two theories lies at the heart of quantum gravity, an endeavor to develop a unified framework that seamlessly integrates quantum mechanics with the geometric nature of spacetime in general relativity. One prominent approach is string theory, which posits that particles are not point-like but rather one-dimensional strings, vibrating in higher-dimensional spaces. Another approach is loop quantum gravity, which attempts to quantize spacetime itself by describing it as a network of discrete loops.

Despite these efforts, a complete theory of quantum gravity remains elusive, and the search for such a theory is a very important quest in theoretical physics today. This ongoing pursuit not only aims to deepen our understanding of the universe but also promises to shed light on fundamental questions about the nature of space, time, and reality itself.

As determined before, a quantisation of gravity is possible while the relationship before simplifies in many ways, including:

$$\left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right) \cdot \left(V_{R,t} \cdot \left(\frac{c^4}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}\right)\right) \cdot \left(\left(R - \left(\frac{R \cdot D}{2}\right) + (\Lambda \cdot D)\right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t)\right) \quad (155)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &+ \left(\frac{v}{c}\right) \cdot \left(V_{R,t} \cdot \left(\frac{c^4}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}\right)\right) \cdot \left(\left(R - \left(\frac{R \cdot D}{2}\right) + (\Lambda \cdot D)\right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t)\right) \\ &= E_{R,t} \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \\ &= V_{R,t} \cdot T \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \\ &= \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t}\right) \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \\ &= \hat{H} \cdot \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (156) \end{aligned}$$

This model of gravity quantization aims, among other objectives, to facilitate experimental inquiries into Kant's concept of the thing-in-itself, potentially bridging metaphysical theories with empirical science.

4. Discussion

Kant's critical philosophy set limits on what we can know about the world, drawing a strict line between the knowable realm of *phenomena* and the inaccessible realm of *noumena*. These boundaries have become entrenched, forming what we might term 'epistemological red lines.' These red lines have dominated Western philosophy and science for centuries, shaping the very way readers think about the relationship between knowledge and objective reality.

The Limits of Kantian Epistemology

Yet, as we progress scientifically, it is time to question these limits. Are these 'epistemological red lines' truly as impermeable as Kant believed? Can we not move beyond the knowable to the unknowable, and in doing so, embrace a broader, more inclusive understanding of objective reality? As long as we can rightfully rely on the Pythagorean Theorem and the insights of Einstein's Special Theory of Relativity, we have a duty to emphasize the need to break free from the long-considered insurmountable limits imposed by Kant's philosophy. Kant drew a sharp 'red' line between the realm of knowable phenomena and unknowable noumena, and challenging Kant's inappropriate concept of the relationship between the known and unknown can be seen as necessary to push the boundaries of epistemology. The time has come to dismantle Kant's epistemological red lines. The limitations placed on what we can and cannot know, defined by Kant's system, restrict the development of alternative epistemologies. Moving beyond Kant's boundaries invites a reconsideration of the nature of knowledge itself, offering the possibility of richer, more dynamic understandings of objective reality.

Moving Beyond the Red Lines

To move beyond Kant's epistemological red lines is to challenge the very structure of knowledge. This is not simply a rejection of Kant but a necessary evolution of our scientific possibilities. By questioning these established boundaries, we can open the door to new and dynamic form of relationship between the known and unknown that do not rest on Kant's rigid distinctions but allow for the fluid and interconnected nature of reality.

The call to move beyond Kantian epistemology invites a rethinking of the possibilities of knowledge. It asks us to explore what lies beyond the borders of Kant's framework and consider epistemologies that embrace the full complexity of human experience and objective reality.

5. Conclusion

A forward-looking approach that explores new or alternative frameworks beyond Kantian epistemology in order to challenge Kant's limitations on what can be known is certainly provocative. However, based on the Pythagorean theorem, Euclid's altitude theorem, and Einstein's special theory of relativity, we have reason to

'consider Kantian epistemology as relative and confined within its own limits. '

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

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Associated Data

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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